

Open Source Platform for Scalable Multi-Purpose Virtual Desktop Infrastructures

A basic service for NFDI consortia

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Abstract

Data and access to it are central to each NFDI consortium. However, moving data around is often impractical—it may be too large, sensitive, or restricted by agreements with, e.g., the funding provider, and copying introduces duplication, versioning issues, and loss of provenance. Rather than bringing data to the researcher, a Desktop-as-a-Service (DaaS) approach can offer researchers interactive, high-performance access in a secure and efficient manner. Driven by the need for seamless workflows and efficient data handling in NFDI4BIOIMAGE [1], we present a DaaS approach that is broadly applicable across NFDI.[2] It supports diverse use cases, such as standardized virtual training environments for distributed participants (like required in DataPLANT [3], [4]), remote visualization of large-scale HPC datasets, and secure access to sensitive data (BERD)—all without the overhead of local machine setup and maintenance.

Our DaaS concept[5] aligns with ongoing shifts toward centralized, cloud-like infrastructures and offers an alternative to distributed hardware management. Benefits include flexible provisioning of varied software environments, simplified administration, improved access control and security, better resource utilization, and support for green IT initiatives. At its core, the DaaS provides users with access to guest systems via hardware-accelerated remote protocols, enhancing the experience for 3D and graphically demanding applications. Our implementation builds a sustainable, fully open-source solution by integrating five key components using existing tools:

- **Unified Access Gateway:** A central (web) portal provides seamless entry to all DaaS resources. Non-technical users can launch customized virtual machines (VMs) tailored to their research needs.
- **Template Management:** Service stewards or administrators can create, upload, and share reusable VM templates adapted to specific scientific workflows or tasks, allowing users to seamlessly use their preferred operating systems and existing software.
- **Efficient Remote Display:** A host-based mechanism captures the VM framebuffer and transmit it as a video stream using hardware-accelerated encoding via the SPICE protocol, which also supports USB forwarding, bidirectional audio, and printer sharing.

- Hardware-Accelerated Rendering: Suitable GPUs¹ supporting SR-IOV (Single Root I/O Virtualization) are partitioned into virtual functions, allowing for high flexibility, scalability, and utilization of hardware resources². These virtual functions are directly passed through as PCI devices to VMs using VFIO, enabling high-performance 3D graphics and video processing. Open-source drivers are preferred for sustainability and compatibility. [6]
- Short- and Long-Term Scheduling: Integration with different virtualization environments or workflow engines such as Galaxy enables effective resource scheduling for large-scale remote desktop sessions. [7]

After more than three years of analysis and prototyping, we have developed a functional DaaS prototype utilizing SPICE and GPU passthrough. It enables fast remote desktops and interactive visualization by directly accessing the VM framebuffer and accelerating both encoding and rendering. This architecture overcomes the limitations of traditional open-source remote protocols like VNC, X11, or Xpra, supporting demanding visualization and imaging use cases.

In addition, we are developing a web-based remote access gateway for user authentication, authorization, and workflow management—further simplifying the deployment and usability of DaaS across research communities.

Resources

- Access-restricted public demo server³
- Public GitLab resources of DaaS⁴
- SPICE patches for dma-buf video encoding merged⁵
- QEMU patches submitted by Intel Engineer, Vivek Kasireddy⁶
- Ansible GPU node setup process⁷
- GStreamer patches for efficient encoding using GPU hardware acceleration^{8 9 10}

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¹Our current setup uses the Intel Flex 140/170 GPUs (<https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/products/docs/discrete-gpus/data-center-gpu/flex-series/vdi-solution-brief.html>), which enable SR-IOV without additional licensing fees.

²Most GPUs will allow static assignment of VRAM to virtual functions and dynamic assignment of GPU computing time.

³<https://demo.osvdi.uni-freiburg.de/>, user: user1, password: pass1

⁴<https://gitlab.uni-freiburg.de/opensourcevdi>

⁵<https://lists.freedesktop.org/archives/spice-devel/2025-February/053761.html>

⁶<https://mail.gnu.org/archive/html/qemu-devel/2025-04/msg05481.html>

⁷<https://gitlab.uni-freiburg.de/opensourcevdi/ansible-intel-gpu>

⁸<https://gitlab.freedesktop.org/gstreamer/gstreamer/-/commit/f77189a7bf9442c5cd94a801a6b39dded5bcd4d4>

⁹<https://gitlab.freedesktop.org/gstreamer/gstreamer/-/commit/671281d860899e9a236f604076831a9ce72186b8>

¹⁰<https://gitlab.freedesktop.org/gstreamer/gstreamer/-/commit/b1cda4439bc9170b4af60ab464471f58ea770f58>

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